

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPLEMENTATION OF AN INNOVATIVE COMPUTERIZED EDUCATIONAL
PROGRAM ON SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED INFECTIONS FOR A HIGH SCHOOL
HEALTH CENTER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this project was to use the existing evidence to implement and evaluate an interactive computerized educational program on sexually transmitted infections for a high school health center. This researcher constructed the program from a teaching tool template based on the popular game show *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire*. Students who visited the clinic were from a large urban high school in Los Angeles, California, and were asked to view and evaluate the computer program. This study had 55 patient participants (16 males and 39 females) who completed a 7-question, 5-point Likert-type scale questionnaire where 1 = *strongly disagreed* and 5 = *strongly agreed*. The students were asked if they found the program usable, understandable, and enjoyable. Students were also asked if they had accessed similar programs previously and whether they felt they learned new information on STIs and HIV. Average mean scores with their standard deviations were calculated for each item. Results indicated that the program was mostly well received by these patients, with the lowest score indicating that they had not necessarily accessed similar types of programs in the past ($M = 2.3$, $SD = 1.1$). With the significance set at 0.05, an independent samples t test found there were no significant differences between male and female responses on all the questions. For Questions 1-6, there were also no significant differences found between age groups. However, on Question 7, when students were asked whether they enjoyed the program, there was a significant difference, $t(53) = -2.28$, $p = 0.026$, between the two age groups.

This result showed that the younger aged patients (14-16 years) found the program more enjoyable than the older adolescent group (17-19 years).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	iii
LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Incidence of STIs in Adolescents	3
HIV Risk	4
School-Based Clinics: Funding and Patient Confidentiality	5
Computerized Education in the Clinical Setting.....	7
Problem Statement.....	9
Purpose of the Project	9
Clinical Question	10
LITERATURE REVIEW	11
High-Risk Sexual Behavior in Adolescents.....	12
Acculturation of Hispanic Adolescents and Sexual Behavior	16
Computers and Sexual Health Information Seeking by Adolescents	19
Summary of Literature Review.....	23
Theoretical Framework and Model.....	24
Individual Characteristics and Experiences	26
Prior Related Behavior.....	26
Personal Factors and Importance of Health	26
Perceived Benefits of Action	27
Perceived Barriers to Action.....	28
Perceived Self-Efficacy	28
Activity Related Affect.....	29
METHODOLOGY	32
Project Subjects and Setting	32
Selection of Computer Educational Program by Expert Panel and Student Board	34

Tools and Budget	36
Intervention and Data Collection	37
Ethical Considerations	38
DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.....	40
Gender Differences	41
Age Group Comparison	42
DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS	44
Project Limitations.....	46
Implications for Nursing.....	48
Implications for Future Research.....	49
Conclusion	50
REFERENCES	52
APPENDIX A: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL: ACCULTURATION OF HISPANIC ADOLESCENTS AND HIGH-RISK SEXUAL BEHAVIORS	59
APPENDIX B: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL: ADOLESCENTS AND HIGH-RISK SEXUAL BEHAVIORS.....	63
APPENDIX C: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL: COMPUTERS AND HEALTH INFORMATION SEEKING BY ADOLESCENTS	66
APPENDIX D: EVALUATION OF COMPUTER LEARNING PROGRAM FOR SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED INFECTIONS.....	70
APPENDIX E: INFORMATION LETTER.....	71

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Evaluation of Various Computer Programs by Student Board.....	36
2. Summary of Independent Samples t Tests: Comparisons of Males and Females	42
3. Summary of Independent Samples t Tests: Comparisons of Students Aged 14-16 and Students Aged 17-19.....	43

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Mean scores and <i>SD</i> for all patient responses to questionnaire (1 = <i>strongly disagree</i> and 5 = <i>strongly agree</i> ; <i>N</i> = 55).	41

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BACKGROUND

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and the increased risk for contracting the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) are a growing problem among the adolescent population in the United States, as tracked and reported by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Approximately 20 million new STIs are reported every year, with half of these occurring in 15- to 24-year-olds (CDC, 2013c). Homosexual and bisexual men as well as young adults are responsible for the largest number of newly diagnosed cases of STIs and HIV each year (CDC, 2013c). The African American/Black population, followed by the Hispanic/Latino population, has the highest rates of chlamydia, gonorrhea, and syphilis infections in the United States (CDC, 2013c).

Adolescence is also a time of physical and psychosocial upheaval; as bodies change, there is increased sexual awareness and peer groups become increasingly more important. Feelings of invincibility and egocentric behavior can also emerge during this developmental stage (Wickman, Anderson, & Greenberg, 2008). Earlier initiation of sexual intercourse, decreased use of condoms, and increased use of drugs and alcohol are some of the many high-risk behaviors of adolescents (CDC, 2013c). Teenagers in an egocentric phase run a higher risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases because the majority of them never worry about the consequences of their actions (Martin & Sokol, 2011; Wickman et al., 2008). However, many adolescents refuse or are hesitant to seek health care regarding sexual issues because of their fear of parental retribution, worries about inability to pay for care, and inaccessibility to clinics or providers (Perry et al., 2012).

As part of the answer to this problem, school-based health centers (SBHCs) have been formed to provide care with strict patient confidentiality and without charge to adolescents for services related to their sexual health. These centers also referred to as school-based clinics, frequently deal with the medical and psychosocial needs of adolescents (Santelli et al., 2003). There are approximately 1,900 school-based clinics in the United States that are located in the following areas: 57% urban, 27% rural, and 16% suburban. These clinics are mostly located in middle schools and high schools and are usually run by a community health clinic (28%), hospital (25%), public health department (15%), and the school system itself (12%). Ethnic minorities (70%) are the largest adolescent population served by these clinics. Due to the high number of adolescents who initiate sex between the ages of 15 and 19 years, these clinics function to serve a very high-risk population that is vulnerable to STIs and HIV (Keeton, Soleimanpour, & Brindis, 2012; Kirby & Coyle, 1997; Santelli et al., 2003; Sebastian, Ramos, Fairbrother, & McGrath, 2013).

Many school-based clinics, especially those that primarily serve high school students, offer family planning services, STI testing, STI treatment, pregnancy testing and counseling, and patient education as well as general medical, nutritional, and mental health services (Keeton et al., 2012). However, even with the creation of these clinics, the incidence of STIs continues to rise. Patient education via pamphlets, videos, and face-to-face provider patient education has always been an important component of these clinics. Increased knowledge through patient education about STIs does not necessarily lead to long-standing changes in high-risk sexual behaviors, but it can improve an

adolescent's chance of making better and more informed decisions about prevention (Bull, Levine, Black, Schmiede, & Santelli, 2012).

Computers and digital media are very popular with the adolescent population. Teens frequently access the Internet and social media sites several times a day (O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011). Recently, more researchers have been looking into the possibility of using computerized programs and social media sites as innovative and interactive ways of introducing important health education topics that would serve as an adjunct to the adolescent patient-provider visit (Allison et al., 2012). The purpose of this project was to use the research evidence to construct, implement, and evaluate a computerized educational program that could potentially raise awareness, increase patient screening for STIs, and improve prevention for the adolescent patients who visit a high school health center in Los Angeles, California.

Incidence of STIs in Adolescents

Chlamydia is the STI most frequently reported in the adolescent population of the United States. In 2012, the incidence of chlamydia in California was high, with rates of 445 cases per 100,000 population (CDC, 2013c). In 2009, depending on the various high schools covered by the Los Angeles Unified School District, there can be an average of 133-4,752 cases of chlamydia per 100,000 reported. This data showed the importance of establishing SBHCs in some areas of Los Angeles, California (Los Angeles Unified School District, 2009). In 2010, the state of California reported 150,443 new cases of chlamydia. In 2011, the state of California reported 166,773 new cases of chlamydia. There was an increase of 16,330 or 10% in 1 year. Similarly, in 2010, in the metropolitan statistical areas of Los Angeles, Long Beach, and Santa Ana alone, there were 56,033

new cases. In 2011, these same areas reported 58,552 cases, showing an increase of 2,519 or 5% in 1 year (CDC, 2013c).

Gonorrhea is the second most reported STI in the adolescent group. In 2010, the state of California saw 26,441 new cases of gonorrhea (CDC, 2013c). However, in 2011, there were a reported 27,516 new cases. This showed an increase of 1,075 cases or 4% in 1 year. For the metropolitan statistical areas of Los Angeles, Long Beach, and Santa Ana, there were 11,156 new cases in 2010 and 11,105 new cases in 2011, actually showing a decrease of 51 cases (CDC, 2013c).

Syphilis is also on the rise in the state of California, with 6,115 new cases reported in 2010 and 6,782 new cases in 2011. This was a rise of 667 cases or 10%. In the metropolitan statistical areas of Los Angeles, Long Beach, and Santa Ana, there was a rise of 110 cases from 2010 to 2011(CDC, 2013c).

HIV Risk

STIs increase the risk of HIV infection (Bradley et al., 2013; CDC, 2013a). In 2010, the largest percentage of new HIV infections were in the 25- to 34-year age group, with 31% or 14,500 cases, followed closely by the 13- to 24-year age group, with 26% or 12,200 cases. African Americans followed by Latinos have the highest rate of new HIV infections (CDC, 2013a). STIs increase a person's risk of acquiring HIV in several ways: they can cause cellular changes that can make it easier for HIV to enter the body, as in the case of being infected with syphilis or the herpes virus, or they can cause inflammation, which then triggers our body's immune system, as seen in persons infected with chlamydia or gonorrhea. These infections weaken the body and make it more susceptible to HIV. However, even knowing that STIs can lead to a higher propensity for

contracting HIV, providers are not ordering the HIV test as often as they should. In a recent study, less than 51% of persons who tested positive for STIs were also tested for HIV (Bradley et al., 2013). Although the STI gets treated, HIV remains undiagnosed and therefore can infect unsuspecting sexual partners.

Most STIs are treatable, but if undiagnosed and untreated, they can lead to pelvic inflammatory disease in women and infertility in both men and women (CDC, 2013b). Multiple sexual partners, men having sex with men, and the act of having unprotected sex are the key variables that will lead to STI and HIV infection (CDC, 2013c). Even if an STI is treated, the threat of reinfection can occur if the patient is exposed again through sexual contact. There is currently no cure for HIV. If infected with this virus, it can lead to increased patient morbidity and mortality.

School-Based Clinics: Funding and Patient Confidentiality

Most adolescents are dependent on their parents and therefore worry about lack of confidentiality regarding treatment for STIs or family planning issues (Perry et al., 2012). Nationally, Title X, Public Law 91-572 Population Research and Voluntary Family Planning Programs, is a federal, discretionary public health program that serves millions of low-income Americans and minors by providing family planning and STI testing for males and females in the age group of 13-44 years without charge (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2013). In the state of California, the Minor's Medical Care Consent Law, known as Assembly Bill (AB) 499, protects minors 12 years and older and gives them the ability to consent to confidential medical services regarding diagnosis, treatment, and education on the prevention of STIs and HIV (Assembly Bill No. 499). Minors are also allowed to receive confidential care for reproductive health, mental

health, and substance abuse treatment. Together, Title X and AB 499 make it possible for minors to not only receive care regarding their sexual health issues, they also protect a minor's right to privacy since health care providers are not permitted to share information regarding STI testing, HIV testing, results, or treatment without the minor's written consent (Assembly Bill No. 499). Title X also covers those minors who choose to come for sexual health and family planning counseling even if they are covered under their parents' health insurance. Insurance companies must share claims information about any patient treatment with the primary policyholder (English, Gold, Nash, & Levine, 2012). This would reveal to parents or guardians exactly what the minor was seen and treated for when they receive their bill or explanation of benefits forms, thereby revealing all of the adolescent's confidential information (English et al., 2012). While providers may encourage patients to have open conversations regarding their sexual health with a trusted adult, parent, or perhaps another supportive family member, if adolescents choose to keep the information confidential, it is their prerogative. These laws were primarily put in place to encourage adolescents to come in for free and confidential family planning services as well as STI and HIV testing and treatment as a way to reduce the increased incidence of diseases and teen pregnancy in the high-risk, vulnerable population.

More than 70% of the students who utilize SBHCs are ethnic minorities (Keeton et al., 2012). For many students, these clinics serve as their primary center for health care (Keeton et al., 2012). Hispanics are the largest ethnic minority group in the United States. They are the largest minority group, 36.8% nationally, that frequent many of these school-based clinics (Larson, Sandelowski, & McQuiston, 2012; Strozer, Juszczak, & Ammerman, 2010). By the year 2050, Hispanics will make up 29% of the U.S.

population (Passel & Cohn, 2008). National statistics reveal that Hispanic youth have higher rates of unprotected sex and that Hispanic females have one of the highest rates of teen pregnancy amongst the major ethnic groups (Reyes & Elias, 2011). About 70% of the patients who frequent SBHCs in Los Angeles County are ethnic minorities and come from households that have incomes less than 133% of the federal poverty level (Los Angeles Unified School District, 2009). Hispanic students are the largest ethnic group that seeks services at this high school health center.

However, even with programs funded by Title X, confidentiality protected by AB 499, and the increased presence of SBHCs, the rate of STIs and HIV in the adolescent population continues to climb. Providers are always attempting to find better methods to prevent this rising problem. Patient education is an important intervention for any student visiting a SBHC. A Title X funded clinic is mandated to offer and document patient education regarding high-risk sexual behavior at every preventative health care patient visit (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2013). Pamphlets on teen pregnancy, STIs, and HIV are usually placed in both the waiting and exam rooms. These pamphlets can still be a good way to get information to the patient if the patient actually reads them. Effective patient education does more than just dispense medical information. The information must be seen as relevant and age and culturally appropriate and appeal to the senses (Deccache, 1995).

Computerized Education in the Clinical Setting

Computerized patient education programs in the clinical setting are becoming increasingly more popular because they can easily meet many learning objectives. Some clinics have Facebook pages or websites where patients can easily access information on

their own computers when they need it and at their convenience (Jones & Biddlecom, 2011). Young adults increasingly utilize computers and information technology for research and education (Wang, Luo, Gao, & Kong, 2012; Williams, 2005). Lenhart, Purcell, Smith, and Zickuhr (2010) reported that of the youth surveyed between the ages of 12 and 17 years, 93% used social media, those teens from households with less than \$30,000 incomes were more likely to use social networking more often than teens from higher income families, 80% owned a game console, and 51% owned a portable game console.

Many elementary and secondary schools are beginning to place digital or computerized educational programs in the classroom to enhance student learning (O’Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011). Digital education programs are not utilized as a way to replace the teacher, textbooks, or reading material, but as a new, innovative way to engage the student and improve learning (Yuan-Hsuan, Waxman, Jiun-Yu, Michiko, & Lin, 2013). Young adults are the most frequent visitors to social media sites like Facebook or Twitter, where they gather and exchange information with friends, family members, and other individuals. They also access the Internet for information about their schoolwork, relationships, health, and various other interests (O’Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011). A recent poll by Common Sense Media (2012) showed that 51% of teenagers log on to their favorite social media at least once a day, with approximately 34% logging on more than several times a day.

Rideout, Foehr, and Roberts (2010), as part of their work for the Kaiser Family Foundation, polled 2002 third-12th graders regarding their use of digital media. In a subgroup of boys and girls in Grades 7-12 they found that more than half (55%) said they

have looked up health information online for themselves or for someone they knew. Among older teens, 15- to 18-year-olds, 62% looked up health information online more often than have watched TV (49%), listened to the radio (45%), or posted videos online (22%). Educational computerized programs, especially if they are interactive and challenge teens to actively take part in the learning process, can empower adolescents with the knowledge to improve their health and modify their high-risk behaviors (Brown, Halpern, & L'Engle, 2005; Gilliam et al., 2011).

Problem Statement

Even with the availability of SBHCs, which provide access to family planning services, protection of a minor's confidentiality, and information via pamphlets, videos, and face-to-face education between the patient and provider, STI rates are still climbing in the adolescent, especially the ethnic minority, population. The CDC (2013c) has stated that in the past few years, chlamydia and gonorrhea have been and still continue to be the most commonly reported STIs for the 15- to 24-year age group. Adolescents often engage in high-risk sexual behaviors that can lead to an increase in STIs and HIV. STIs that go undiagnosed and untreated can lead to an increase in pelvic inflammatory disease in females and infertility in both genders. STIs can also lead to higher rates of HIV transmission across the infected cells and ultimately lead to increased patient morbidity and mortality rates.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this study was to implement and evaluate a computerized educational program that could potentially raise awareness, increase patient screening, and improve prevention for STIs and HIV for the adolescent patients who visit a high

school health center in Los Angeles, California. This program would be the first computerized educational program in this clinic and serve as an adjunct to the current methods of patient education.

Clinical Question

Will students in a high school health center find the implementation of an innovative, interactive computer-based patient education program on STIs and HIV to be useable, informative, and enhance knowledge? Will there be a significant difference between gender and age group responses when evaluating the computerized educational program? Based on the outcome and utilization of this program, could it potentially lead to improved screening, use of protection, and decreased high-risk sexual behaviors?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The content for this literature review is a result of a combined search of PubMed, CINAHL, ScienceDirect, PsychInfo, Google, and Yahoo electronic databases and search engines. The literature for review was found using the following terms: *adolescent and high-risk sexual behaviors, computer-based education on sexually transmitted diseases, computer use and adolescents, acculturation and sexual behaviors of Hispanic adolescents, and school-based health centers*. There were 5,025 articles found in the category of adolescents and sexual behaviors. There were 77 articles found on computer-based education of sexually transmitted diseases, with three being systematic reviews of computer-based websites on STIs and HIV. There were 1,085 articles on Hispanics and sexual behaviors, 719 articles on school-based clinics, and 3,261 articles on computer use by adolescents. Each article met the following criteria: published no later than 2005, unless it was a significant or well-referenced study or if it contained information written by someone significant in the field of adolescent behavior; written in English; and peer reviewed. This researcher reviewed the following number of articles: a total of 24 articles on computer-based education on sexually transmitted diseases, with six research studies that focused on adolescents using computers for STI education; 14 articles, seven of them research studies, on Hispanic adolescent acculturation and high-risk sexual behaviors; six articles on school-based clinics; and 21 articles, five of which were research studies, on adolescents and high-risk sexual behaviors. The levels of evidence for these studies include qualitative studies, randomized controlled trials, quasi-experimental designs, literature reviews, and cohort studies. All research articles and their findings are listed in the Table of Evidence (Appendices A, B, and C). In addition

to these articles and research studies, information from two books and various websites on these same topics were reviewed and data were utilized for portions of this paper.

High-Risk Sexual Behavior in Adolescents

High-risk sexual behaviors by the youth of this country are of growing concern. Adolescents are experiencing sex at an earlier age and with multiple partners (Brown et al., 2005; Santelli, Abraido-Lanza, & Melnikas, 2009) and infection rates for chlamydia and gonorrhea are climbing (CDC, 2013c). In the United States, 46% of high school students have had sexual intercourse at least once and only 61% of them reported using a condom (Perry et al., 2012). Females in the age group of 15-24 years have the highest rates of chlamydia and gonorrhea (CDC, 2013c; Perry et al., 2012). In the adolescent population, 1 in 4 sexually active youth in the United States will have been infected with an STI and/or HIV by age 24 and, worldwide, about half of all HIV infections will have occurred in men and women age 25 or less (Gilbert, Temby, & Rogers, 2005).

Wickman et al. (2008), in their qualitative study of 10 multiethnic teens on the concept of adolescent beliefs of invincibility, found that teens had certain ideas about moving from childhood to adolescence. They assessed the following common themes related to adolescence: the difficulty of transitioning from being carefree to having increased responsibilities, frequent thoughts of being invincible, the difficulties of finding balance in life between good and bad situations, and the dilemmas of participating in high-risk but pleasurable behaviors. When someone sees himself or herself as invincible, he or she may not see he or she is at an actual risk for getting an STI. Adolescents reported a feeling of being high when doing something risky and enjoyed the rush of adrenaline related to gaining immediate gratification when it came to sex.

Adolescents often speak about living in the present and not always thinking about the consequences of their actions, which researchers have called hedonistic tendencies (Li & Wright, 2014). Many adolescents also feel that peer pressure could potentially lead them to do things they may not normally do as an attempt to fit in and be socially accepted (Ethier, Kershaw, Niccolai, Lewis, & Ickovics, 2003; Gullette & Lyons, 2005; Michael & Ben-Zur, 2007). This perception of invincibility, seeking immediate gratification, succumbing to peer pressure, and developing a *personal fable* are normal stages in the cognitive development of an adolescent (Elkind, 1967). Child psychologist, Dr. D. Elkind, first conceptualized this theory and called it egocentrism (Elkind, 1967). Adults may see the teenage years as very stressful and tumultuous, but an egocentric adolescent may describe his or her world as perfectly normal and stable (Alberts, Elkind, & Ginsberg, 2007). This is one explanation as to why adolescents have a greater chance of participating in high-risk sexual behavior and contracting STIs. Dr. Elkind (1967) stated that egocentrism eventually fades as the adolescent grows older and his or her *personal fables* no longer exist or are contradicted, for instance, when someone gets an STI or HIV or finds herself pregnant due to high-risk sexual behaviors. Reducing high-risk behaviors that have immediate gratification to those that are not immediately gratifying can be difficult to accept during this developmental phase and adolescents may require guidance on how to accomplish this change (Alberts et al., 2007).

Knowledge of contracting STIs does not necessarily correlate with behavior change. A longitudinal study by Secor-Turner, McMorris, Sieving, and Bearinger (2013) that surveyed females between the ages of 14 and 17 years reported that females with at least one of the following risk factors—family instability, substance abuse, involvement

with domestic violence, and sexual abuse—were significantly more likely to have an increased number of sexual partners when assessed 6 months later compared to females without any of these risk factors ($p < 0.05$). However, these individual risk factors were not significantly associated with consistent condom use 6 months later even though it was determined that these adolescents understood about STI prevention. Unfortunately, other studies have reported similar relationships between risk factors and condom use (L'Engle & Jackson, 2008; Schwartz et al., 2012; Villarruel, Jemmott, Jemmott, & Ronis, 2007).

Goodson, Buhi, and Dunsmore (2006) did a systematic review of the literature regarding self-esteem and high-risk sexual behavior. They found that 72% of the studies reported that the relationship between a teenager's self-esteem and behavior was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). However, a descriptive study by Ronis and O'Sullivan (2011) did show that adolescent females were at a higher risk of initiating unsafe sex due to increased alcohol intake and decreased religious beliefs. Adolescent males had a higher risk of initiating unsafe sex if they had decreased self-esteem and decreased religious beliefs.

The age of a person's first initiation of sex is a topic of interest for many providers and researchers. A longitudinal study done by L'Engle and Jackson (2008) attempted to identify those factors that might predict an adolescent's susceptibility to having sex sooner and without protection. Using a logistic regression analysis, they found that out of 854 adolescents in Grades 7 and 8 interviewed, 28% were predicted to have a higher susceptibility to early initiation of sex. The factors that were associated with adolescents' increased susceptibility were being more physically mature, greater expression of feelings and competency, perception that peers are sexually active,

decreased positive interactions with their family, and decreased religious affiliation. When the same study adolescents were interviewed 2 years later, 23% of the high-risk group had initiated sex. However, this study also reported that relying on a single indicator was not always the best predictor of whether an adolescent will initiate sex. The researchers cautioned that a limitation of this study, as well any type of study that relies on adolescent responses, would be whether the teens fully comprehended the questions. Also, an adolescent's fear of a breach of confidentiality or repercussions from the adults could have lead some to answer the questions less than truthfully. Even simply answering a question regarding sexual preferences can be an issue since an adolescent may identify himself or herself as heterosexual, but, on occasion, may have sex with someone of the same gender. There is also no good way for a researcher to determine whether a person is really using a condom or having sex with multiple partners unless the patient reveals this information; therefore, as providers we have to rely on what the patient tells us (Ethier et al., 2003; Gullette & Lyons, 2005; L'Engle & Jackson, 2008; Michael & Ben-Zur, 2007; Secor-Turner et al., 2013).

Adolescents are more likely to forego medical attention even when they may think they need it. Problems with lack of knowledge of how to access health care, worry about payment for services, issues of confidentiality, peer pressure, lack of transportation, and fear of the providers themselves are all potential barriers that may prevent adolescents from seeking care (Finer & Philbin, 2013; Perry et al., 2012).

Henry-Reid et al. (2010) reported in their study of data collected by the surveys sent to members of the American Academy of Pediatricians in 2005, 468 pediatricians stated that only 62% discussed abstinence, 61% discussed condoms and STIs, and 54%

discussed HIV. Most pediatricians (82%) did not discuss sexuality or sexual identity. While 30% prescribed condoms, only 19% provided condom usage demonstrations. Only 46% of the pediatricians ordered any STI testing, while only 28% included HIV testing as well.

Acculturation of Hispanic Adolescents and Sexual Behavior

The Hispanic population is the fastest growing minority population in the United States. California, Texas, and Florida educate approximately 60% of our nation's Hispanic youth. Between 2006 and 2010, Hispanic adolescent high school graduation rates have risen from 61% to 71% (Balfanz, Bridgeland, Bruce, & Fox, 2013). Along with these increased graduation rates, acculturation and incorporation of American ideas have become the norm among young Hispanics. Acculturation of Hispanic teens into the American culture can be a source of conflict for those teens with family members who want them to stay rooted in their Hispanic culture (Champion, Harlin, & Collins, 2013; Reyes & Elias, 2011; Villarruel et al., 2007). In a descriptive study done by Villarruel et al. (2007), *familialism* was discussed as the most important cultural value of the Hispanic culture. It is the idea that a person is always attached to one's family, thereby evoking of sense of loyalty and solidarity with his or her culture. Gender roles are also clearly defined in the Hispanic culture. *Marianismo* is the Hispanic culture's belief that a woman should maintain abstinence until marriage and *machismo* is the belief that men by nature must be strong and have a duty to produce children. Understanding the Hispanic youth's religious faith is also a very important factor when working with this population. A group of 233 male and female adolescents with a mean age of 15.4 years were surveyed in a descriptive study by Villarruel et al. (2007). They found that hedonistic

beliefs, self-efficacy, and partner approval were significant variables ($p < 0.05$) for both genders when thinking about initiating sex. In addition, negotiating with a partner and parental disapproval were significant predictors of intention to use condoms in females. In males, only impulse control, the ability to use and apply a condom during sex, was a significant predictor of intention to use condoms ($p < 0.05$). However, religiosity was significantly correlated with past condom use ($p < 0.05$) and may be a predictor of future condom use. Another descriptive study on condom use in Hispanics found that 53% of the Hispanic adolescents surveyed used condoms because their peers used them (Kapadia et al., 2012).

A descriptive study by Schwartz et al. (2012) examined the effects of acculturation on 302 Hispanic adolescents and their families. In the area of sexuality, adolescent-reported family functioning was positively predictive of sexual activity ($p < 0.02$) as well as unprotected sex ($p < 0.01$). In other words, if the family and the adolescent were on good terms and had open discussions, there were fewer high-risk sexual behaviors. Providers sometimes are confronted with dealing with Hispanic adolescents who are in turmoil because their new beliefs about sexuality no longer match their parents' beliefs. A qualitative phenomenological study by Adams and Williams (2011) reported on themes regarding adolescent sexuality that emerged from interviews with 41 Hispanic and 34 White 16-year-old males and females. Hispanic youth wished that they had known that important familial bonds would change once they became sexually involved with someone. Hispanic females wished that there were more open discussions about sex, pregnancy, and dealing with romantic relationships, especially on how to handle conflict with their partners. Both Hispanic and White males wished that

they knew how to handle their frustration and pain during relationship conflict and breakups. All groups wished that their parents would be more supportive of their need for independence and guide them instead of controlling them through these emotional adolescent times.

In a descriptive study, Unger and Molina (2000) surveyed 291 Hispanic females and found that Latinas who spoke English in the home were at higher risk for STIs due to having four or more lifetime sexual partners than those Latinas who lived in non-English-speaking homes ($p < 0.05$). This was mainly because they felt an increased sense of sexual freedom and willingness to bend to peer pressure as they were rapidly becoming more aware of the social norms of the teens in America. Other studies reported similar findings about how acculturation and resulting family tension in Hispanic adolescents lead to an increase in high-risk sexual behaviors and less condom use (Adams & Williams, 2011; Kapadia et al., 2012; Lee & Hahm, 2010; McDonald, Manlove, & Ikramullah, 2009; Santelli, et al., 2009).

Other authors reported some factors that contributed to high-risk sexual behaviors in Hispanic adolescents to be related to the fact that many Latino parents believe that the school is primarily responsible for teaching their children about health and sexuality since the topic of sex education has been the responsibility of schools in Mexico since the 1960s (Larson et al., 2012; Villarruel et al., 2007). They also reported that young adults from Hispanic households often express feelings of being uncomfortable about discussing their sexuality with their parents or anyone they deem an authority figure and therefore often rely on getting information from their peers (Adams & Williams, 2011; Dittus, Jeffries, De Rosa, Loosier, & Ethier, 2013; Schwartz et al., 2012). Additionally, due to

their immigrant status and lack of proper papers demonstrating their educational history, some Hispanic teens may enter the American school system a little later, placing them in a grade behind their same-aged peers. This makes these teens older than other teens in the same grade. A heightened sense of sexuality can become apparent since they appear and dress more maturely than their younger classmates (Larson et al., 2012; Lee & Hahm, 2010).

Education can be enhanced for minority students when teachers actively learn about their students' culture, life experiences, family, and home life. If health care providers become knowledgeable about their patient's life, including physical, psychosocial, and socioeconomic factors, education can be more individualized and meaningful. This type of culturally sensitive education may bring about more positive changes in the patient and reduce high-risk sexual behaviors (Lam, 2012; Larson et al., 2012; Reyes & Elias, 2011; Unger & Molina, 2000).

Computers and Sexual Health Information Seeking by Adolescents

To date, there are few peer-reviewed articles published on the feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of using computer-based education to promote sexual health (Allison et al., 2012). It has been determined that knowledge does not necessarily correlate with the demonstration of less risky sexual behaviors (Bull et al., 2012). However, without knowledge, an individual cannot make an informed decision to improve his or her health (Allison et al., 2012; Roberto, Zimmerman, Carlyle, & Abner, 2007; Whiteley, Mello, Hunt, & Brown, 2012). An online survey of 1,500 adolescents conducted by Boyar, Levine, and Zensius (2011) reported that 11% of the males and 12% of the females surveyed had researched information on sexually transmitted diseases

online. Another study done by Lenhart et al. (2010), with the Pew Internet Research Group, reported that of the 800 teens surveyed, 17% used computers to search for sensitive health information on drug use, sexual health, or depression. Also, 19% were aged 14-17 years and 22% were girls, while 11% were boys.

This generation of teens often seeks sexual health information from their peers and Internet sites accessed through their computers or mobile phones (Gray, Klein, Noyce, Sesselberg, & Cantrill, 2005; Howard, Davis, & Mitchell, 2011; Rideout et al., 2010). However, not all Internet sites are educationally equal or appropriate (Whiteley et al., 2012). Research is just beginning to emerge regarding these websites and their usefulness. A systematic review of websites regarding STIs and HIV conducted by Noar, Clark, Cole, and Lustria (2006) listed a group of websites specifically designed to address adolescent sexual health issues. The goal of this study was to review how these websites addressed the target audience and provide safe sex messages. Theoretical strategies utilized to enhance knowledge and level of interactivity included in the program were also identified as factors contributing to effective messaging. The websites had to be in English, target adolescents or young adults, and include at least two interactive screens. From all the sites searched, only 21 met these criteria. The results of their findings regarding these websites were as follows: 86% targeted teens; 48% included the gay and lesbian lifestyle; 67% encouraged abstinence; 67% addressed medical information regarding STIs, with 57% of those also linking the user to a secondary site that spoke about HIV; 95% showed how to use condoms; and 100% used the threat of getting a sexually transmitted disease as a reason to have safe sex. A few of these websites also had topics on the importance of decreasing the number of sexual partners, changing high-

risk sexual behaviors, speaking honestly with your partner about past sexual history, and delaying the initiation of sexual encounters.

Websites that tailor STI prevention education to the adolescent population can prove to be a cost-effective and innovative way to provide patient education (Gilbert et al., 2005; Noar et al., 2006; Whiteley et al., 2012). Factors such as primary language spoken, reading ability, accessibility of computers, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors must all be taken into account when choosing or developing an interactive patient education program. A hospital-based teen clinic that implemented a computer learning program on sexually transmitted diseases and high-risk sexual behaviors found that 98% of teens thought the computers were a good way to promote good health information and that all clinics should have computers for teens to use while they are waiting to see their provider (Howard et al., 2011). Roberto et al. (2007) conducted a quasi-experimental design, pre and posttest control and experimental group study on the effect of a computer-based teaching program on STIs in rural high schools. A pretest related to STI knowledge, condom use, and perceptions on who could get an STI was given to all of the 887 ninth graders who participated in the study. The experimental group participated in a series of computer-based education activities regarding STIs and condom use, while the participants in the control group continued on with whatever sex education they were given in their classes. At the end of 7 weeks, the experimental group scored significantly higher on knowledge level of STIs ($p < 0.05$), condom use ($p < 0.001$), and perceived susceptibility regarding getting STIs ($p < 0.05$) than the control group. Similar studies reported that improved knowledge about STIs lead to increased awareness of high-risk behaviors and did motivate the adolescent to increase condom use, even if only

temporarily (Bull et al., 2012; Kiene & Barta, 2006; Lightfoot, Comulada, & Stover, 2007).

Many educational institutions are now utilizing computers to aid them with teaching students (Guse et al., 2012; Shi, Van Meijgaard, & Simon, 2012; Wang et al., 2012; Yuan-Hsuan et al., 2013). Computer programs specific to the learning needs of the user are rapidly being developed in many education institutions. Some clinics that see adolescents utilize inexpensive and free computer applications, designed by reliable organizations, that were created to educate adolescents about the consequences of high-risk sexual behaviors (Howard et al., 2011; Noar et al., 2006; Whiteley et al., 2012). Sometimes, adolescents will access these programs before visiting a provider so that they can come prepared for the visit with their questions or concerns (Noar et al., 2006). Other adolescents will seek out computer education sites after their clinic visit to look up more information on issues they discussed with their provider (Bull et al., 2012; Howard et al., 2011).

It is recommended that selection of computerized patient education programs for the clinic undergo careful scrutiny for appropriate patient education material. Many of the most popular computerized sexual health patient education programs have been reviewed in the literature for content, ease of use, age appropriateness, and culturally sensitive information (Noar et al., 2006; Whiteley et al., 2012). Popular websites like www.avert.org, www.teensource.org, and www.kidshealth.org are specifically designed to educate teens and provide information about teen pregnancy, STIs, and family planning. These sites, like many similar sites, can be accessed on the Internet by anyone, of any age, without a pass code or payment.

In a qualitative study of 58 teenagers, Jones and Biddlecom (2011) reported that most of the teens had access to the Internet and used it about 30-60 minutes or more per day. These adolescents accessed social media sites like Facebook, Instant Messaging, Instagram, and Twitter. Approximately half of the teenagers studied accessed the Internet for information about family planning and STIs. Most of them knew that they could access these sites, but chose to do so only if they had a specific question or concern. However, they did express that they liked knowing they had the freedom to find these sites if they needed.

Adolescents from low-income families often do not have their own personal computers or iPhones and can only access the Internet or computerized patient teaching applications in schools or clinics. The availability of these programs in an SBHC levels the playing field for these adolescents. In addition to important patient education, use of these clinic computers can give them a sense of empowerment and self-direction by allowing them access to digital information that their peers may take for granted (Guse et al., 2012; Howard et al., 2011).

Summary of Literature Review

This literature review contained studies that were both qualitative and quantitative. Most of the studies reviewed were descriptive in design and used surveys or questionnaires in which the adolescent subjects were self-reporting. Some of these tools required adolescents to use recollection techniques as well as answer whether they intended to participate in future preventative behaviors by practicing abstinence or condom use. Those studies that were quasi-experimental and longitudinal reported that knowledge levels on STIs were similar on pretesting and then higher on posttesting after

the experimental group was exposed to an educational program on STIs. However, even with an increased knowledge base, the studies reviewed reported that increased knowledge of STIs showed immediate but not long-term reduction in high-risk sexual behaviors. Most of the authors hoped that improved knowledge would at least give adolescents the opportunity to recognize the consequences of their high-risk sexual behaviors to change and improve their health, thereby potentially reducing the rate of STIs.

It is important to recognize that there are several themes that run throughout this literature review; knowledge does not necessarily change behavior, but information and education on STIs give adolescents the power to change if they desire. Adolescents are prone to high-risk behaviors due to their developmental stage, feelings of invincibility, and their increased need for immediate gratification or pleasure. Some adolescents feel they need guidance to change behavior. The more acculturated the Hispanic adolescents are, the more susceptible they are to high-risk sexual behaviors. There are certain limitations that are inherent when doing research that involves adolescent self-reporting of high-risk sexual behaviors. There is not much empirical research done about computerized patient education on STIs; however, current data indicate that these types of programs can improve patient knowledge and evoke at least a temporary change in high-risk sexual behaviors. Adolescents are using online sources to seek and validate health information.

Theoretical Framework and Model

In this study, the assessment, implementation, and evaluation of an interactive computer program for adolescents regarding STI recognition and prevention will be

based on the organizing framework of Nola Pender's health promotion model first published in 1982. This model's constructs pulls from the "expectancy-value, Health Belief Model and social cognitive theories" (Rew, 2005, p. 259). It focuses on competence rather than fear as the major force behind change (Pender, Murdaugh, & Parsons, 2006). It was initially created to assist nurses in working with patients across their lifespan. This model focuses on three main areas of health: individual characteristics and experiences, behavior specific conditions and affect, and behavioral outcomes. This is a very useful model for patient educators because it not only looks at the signs and symptoms of a condition but also prevention through behavior modification. Pender's model considers the whole person, taking into account the importance of individualizing health education based on the biological, psychological, and sociological well-being of an individual. Working effectively with adolescents requires that providers know the age, gender, culture, socioeconomic status, health problems, and educational needs of this population. Therefore, Pender's model has constructs useful to set a framework for providers to utilize while working in a school-based clinic.

The major concepts and definitions of Pender's model link individual characteristics and experiences, prior related behaviors, and frequency of similar behaviors in the past. This model believes that for behavior to change, individuals must change how they interact within their environment, something not always easy for an adolescent (Rew, 2005).

Nola Pender's model is structured by seven cognitive-perceptual factors to predict health behaviors (Pender et al., 2006). Examples of applying new knowledge about

sexual health to each category will show how the model benefits the provider when constructing a plan of action or education for the adolescent.

Individual Characteristics and Experiences

Each person brings into any situation his or her personal characteristics and life experiences (Pender et al., 2006). This is important for the health provider to recognize so that he or she will begin to understand what drives certain behaviors and what the patient may value as important. If high-risk sexual behaviors feed a personal need that the patient values, for example, sex as a way to feel self-confident, then the provider will need to help the patient find other ways to feel good about himself or herself without engaging in high-risk sexual behaviors.

Prior Related Behavior

Often, the best predictor of current behavior is the review of the past frequency rates of engaging in the behavior (Pender et al., 2006). Sometimes, the consequences of engaging in high-risk behaviors are not thought through because the behavior has now become automatic or habitual. Breaking this type of habit is not just a process of learning and understanding the consequences, but actually retraining the body or mind to stop the behavior before it restarts. Condom use is often much more frequent right after patient education on prevention of STIs; however, 6 months later, there is a relapse back into a pattern of having unprotected sex (Bull et al., 2012).

Personal Factors and Importance of Health

A successful patient educational plan must incorporate the biological, psychological, and sociocultural needs of the adolescents as well as their attitudes towards health (Pender et al., 2006). The largest group seen here at this high school

health center is mostly Hispanic females, between the ages of 15 and 17 years. They are also from a lower socioeconomic group. For many of these teens, they or their families have recently immigrated to the United States and English is not the primary language spoken in the home. Important health disparities regarding STIs exist between Hispanic and non-Hispanic adolescents. The Hispanics are a close second behind African Americans regarding rising chlamydia, gonorrhea, and HIV rates. More Hispanics report earlier initiation of sex and less use of condoms or other types of contraceptives as compared to non-Hispanic Whites (Santelli et al., 2009).

Perceived Benefits of Action

Each patient must perceive the education about high-risk behavior as necessary and useful (Pender et al., 2006). Pender's et al.'s (2006) review of the literature on studies that used the health promotion model showed that 61% supported the importance or perceived benefits in order to achieve behavior change. Adolescent patients who perceive that the change will directly benefit not only their health but also their interpersonal relationships might be more likely to decrease high-risk sexual behavior. If they are constantly praised for coming into the clinic, offered services, shown by physical exam how their health has improved, and given the ability to assist in designing their treatment plan, they will feel empowered. Adolescents will more often accomplish and adhere to the change if they feel they have some personal sense of control. For example, condom use amongst adolescent males is improved if both partners are encouraged to discuss its use and offered the freedom to work with their providers to explore other options if it does not seem to fit their lifestyle (Manlove, Ikramullah, & Terry-Humen, 2008).

Perceived Barriers to Action

Anticipated barriers by adolescents can dissuade them from changing their high-risk behaviors (Pender et al., 2006). These behaviors may simply continue because of peer pressure or the want and need to believe what their friends say over their provider. The inconvenience of access to health care, cost of health care, difficulty in obtaining condoms, peer pressure, and the thrill of engaging in high-risk behaviors are difficult barriers to overcome in the adolescent population. Pender et al. (2006) reported on studies that utilized the health promotion model; 79% of these studies reported that perceived barriers were indeed a determinant factor of health-promoting behaviors.

Perceived Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is the “judgment of personal capability to organize and carry out a particular course of action” (Pender et al., 2006, p. 53). Of the studies analyzed by Pender et al. (2006), 86% provided support for the importance of self-efficacy as a major determinant of health-promoting behaviors. Adolescents must feel that not engaging in high-risk behaviors is something they intended and initiated. They must value the responsibility of taking care of themselves and, in turn, the providers who care for them must support this self-efficacy. School-based clinics across the country are largely placed in low-income, ethnically diverse areas. They are increasingly being valued not only for the care they provide but also for the work they do to assist adolescents to improve their knowledge so they can make informed and better decisions about their sexual health (Kirby, 2002).

Activity Related Affect

Change that moves an adolescent towards healthier sexual behavior can only come to fruition if it has a positive effect for the adolescent on all levels (Pender et al., 2006). Adolescents will decrease their high-risk sexual behaviors if they perceive that their peers are doing the same. Campaigns to make teens aware and encourage them to empower themselves with good health can be successful if they not only speak to the idea of health but happiness, less anxiety and a brighter future (Pender et al., 2006). Health providers and educators are encouraged to use peer counselors as part of their sexual health education programs. Adolescents respond well and feel freer to discuss their fears, needs, and concerns with someone their own age (Shin & Rew, 2010).

Pender's model also includes five modifying factors: demographic and biological characteristics, interpersonal influences, situational influences, and behavioral factors (Pender et al., 2006). Demographic and biological characteristics involve paying attention to the cultural and biological capabilities that will allow the patient to change. Role modeling from individuals from within the patient's culture or from those who suffer from a similar health condition can sometimes be very effective in encouraging a person to maintain a healthier lifestyle (Pender et al., 2006).

Interpersonal influences include the expectations of others, social support, and modeling. Primary sources of influence on adolescents can be family, peers, significant others, and health care providers (Pender et al., 2006). While situational influences include perceptions of options available to assist with the change and the characteristic of the demand to change by the provider, family, and friends. It also involves whether the individual feels supported through the change by his or her environment (Pender et al.,

2006). For adolescents, their surrounding environment, peer pressure, and friend and adult support or nonsupport will greatly influence whether they will stop engaging in high-risk behaviors that lead to sexually transmitted diseases. The presence of the high school health center, supportive providers, and peer educators in addition to the promotion of new and innovative health education techniques may improve patient compliance and decrease high-risk sexual behaviors.

A patient often expresses his or her intentions to maintain good behavior to satisfy the health care provider (Pender et al., 2006). Identification of specific strategies an adolescent could use to prevent high-risk sexual behavior may assist him or her to prevent a bad situation before it occurs. Providers need to inquire as to what led the teen back into unhealthy behaviors. By having the patient identify those variables, the provider and patient can come up with scenarios or solutions to avoid the repetition of unhealthy behaviors. Pender et al. (2006) also believed it is also important to praise good behavior and educate, not judge or reprimand, when an adolescent slips back into unhealthy behavior patterns. If the adolescent sees that the provider does not give up on him or her, then perhaps he or she will not give up on himself or herself so easily.

Competing demands can often interfere in accomplishing a changed behavior. Often, the demands of peers, their sexual partners, and their environment as well as lack of family support can make patients feel that they have little control over changing their behavior. For example, this is often seen when a teenage girl states that her boyfriend might find another partner if she asks him to wear a condom. Preferences are those behaviors that teens have more control over (Pender et al., 2006). Behaviors like coming

in regularly for STI testing, having their partners tested, obtaining free condoms, and utilizing birth control are those actions within their control and should be encouraged.

Health-promoting behavior is the endpoint or outcome from appropriate intervention. It is the point where the change has now become a more permanent part of the patient's life. The provider must recognize that patient education of adolescents is just as important as the physical exam. It takes understanding and the willingness by the provider to work closely with the population of the clinic so that patients internalize the change and hopefully engage in a less risky form of sexual behavior.

METHODOLOGY

Project Subjects and Setting

The population of study is adolescents between the ages of 14 and 19 years who attend a large urban high school in Los Angeles, California. These teens are in ninth through 12th grades and are seen at the high school health center. Although this clinic sits on the high school grounds, it is managed and staffed by a local neighborhood family practice clinic. Therefore, students seen at this high school health center are also considered patients of this family practice clinic. The high school health center sits in a permanently placed freestanding structure in the back parking lot of the school. There is a front reception and waiting area, two exam rooms, a laboratory, and a medication area. It employs a clinic director, two nurse practitioners, one family practice physician, one front office assistant director, and a medical attendant. Students who are seen are enrolled in the Family Planning, Access, Care and Treatment (FPACT) Program if the nature of their visit involves their sexual health. Therefore, students are not asked to pay for the visit or any services provided related to these types of visits. This clinic also operates under Title X and AB 499; therefore, all services related to sexual health are kept confidential and can only be transmitted to other parties if the adolescent consents to release of information.

Although the high school is in the county of Los Angeles, California, for the purpose of protecting those minors involved in this study, the exact name of the school will not be revealed. The 2012-2013 accreditation report of the high school where the health clinic of study was located reported the following regarding this large urban high school: there are over 3,000 students; 72.5% of the student body applied and received

free or reduced meal plans because their household incomes were at or below poverty level; and the ethnic makeup of students are 67% Hispanic, 11.4% Filipino, 9.4% Asian, and 9.5% White.

The majority of the student or patient visits in this school-based clinic involve sexual health. This high school does offer mandated health classes that are built into the curriculum where the topics of STIs, HIV, birth control, and abstinence are discussed. It is against the law for any public school in California to offer abstinence-only education (California Education Code 51903-51939). The school and the faculty are very supportive of this clinic. This clinic is also part of the high school's website, acknowledging the clinic's presence to the community, parents, and students. Sometimes, faculty brings students to tour the clinic as well. There is also an active SBHC student board associated with this clinic that is comprised of students from the high school. They hold monthly meetings, serve as peer counselors, and often have sexual health fairs during recess and lunch hours. During these fairs, they discuss STI testing, pregnancy counseling, condom use, and the general function of the clinic. These students are counseled, educated, and supervised by the clinic's director.

Clinic records show that the majority of this SBHC's patients are female, Hispanic, and within the ages of 15-19 years. Unpublished clinic data collected between 1-1-2011 and 12-31-2011 reported the following: there were 770 patient visits to the clinic (86 males and 684 females all between the ages of 15 and 19 years), 88.8% of the clients were females, 76.1% were between the ages of 15 and 17 years, 81.4% were Hispanic, 418 were tested for STIs and HIV, and three males and five females tested positive for the chlamydia. There were no HIV positive patients. The latest unpublished

clinic data collected between the 6-month period of 1-1-2012 and 6-30-2012 reported the following: there were 318 patient visits (21 males and 297 females between the ages of 15 and 19 years), 93.3% were females, 74.8% were between the ages of 15 and 17 years, 79.2% were Hispanic, and one male and four females tested positive for chlamydia. There were also no HIV positive patients at this time. From 2011 to the first half of 2012, there was already a 25% increase in the number of patients diagnosed with an STI.

Selection of Computer Educational Program by Expert Panel and Student Board

Even after an exhaustive search of the literature and computerized educational websites, the few programs specific to STIs were mostly available through Internet access and in the form of PowerPoint presentations, articles, and videos. There were some that had quizzes and games but were only accessible through the Internet as well. This school-based clinic only has Internet access through their hard-wired computers. These computers are for clinic use only and not available for the patients at this time. Portable computers such as laptops and iPads cannot access the Internet unless a portable Internet access device is made available. Although there was discussion by the school district of distributing iPads with limited Internet access in the near future, it was not available for this study.

It was difficult to find a computer education program on STIs that was not Internet based. A total of four programs were brought to the expert panel for review. Two of the programs were created by outside sources, while this researcher created two other programs by using premade computer game templates. Program number one was a PowerPoint CD purchased from an outside vendor that was on STIs and HIV. It did not require the use of the Internet and it was only interactive in the sense that the patient had

to move the slides forward on the computer. This CD had pictures and cartoons drawn by high school students that were accompanied by a well-scripted narrative about STIs. Program number two was an interactive game from a website called www.teensource.com. This site required Internet access that was temporarily provided by this researcher via a portable device. Program number three was an interactive game on STIs that was created by this researcher. It was created from a teaching template based on the game show *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire*. This template was found on a teacher's tools website called www.superteachertools.com. What this researcher created was an interactive multiple-choice game with questions on STIs. It had sound effects, lifelines, and an audience cheering when right answers were selected. With each right answer, the patient received more points or money, with the possibility of reaching 1 million virtual dollars by winning the game. Program number four was a game created in the www.quia.com teaching tools website called *Rags to Riches*, which was a multiple-choice interactive game very similar to *Who Wants to be a Millionaire*. This game had lifelines and virtual money as well but had no sound effects.

All these programs were assessed for color, content accuracy, usability, and graphics by the expert clinic panel, which consisted of the clinic's lead nurse practitioner, the director of the high school health center, and the clinic's student board. The lead practitioner was given access to all the programs to review and while he did not actually select one over another, he consented to using any of them for the study. The clinic director verbally voted in favor of the *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire* STI game. The clinic director and the project director agreed that the student board, which consisted of 10 students, not only view all four programs but rate them as well since they were also

responsible for clinic outreach and represented the peer group of those patients who would eventually participate in the study. They were given a simple evaluation tool where on a scale of 1 to 5, 1 being *poor* and 5 being *excellent*, they were asked to evaluate each program. The *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire* STI game was favored, with the highest average scores in all areas (Table 1).

Table 1

Evaluation of Various Computer Programs by Student Board

Program	Color	Graphics	Usability	Content
STD Video	2.9	2.2	3.4	3.3
Teen Source Game	3.6	2.9	3.7	3.7
STD Millionaire Game ^a	4.3	4.3	4.7	4.8
STD Game (Quia Version)	3.9	3.0	3.9	4.0

Note. These are the average (mean) scores rating the four programs. They are based on feedback from a Likert-type scale (1 = *poor*, 2 = *below average*, 3 = *average*, 4 = *above average*, 5 = *excellent*) by the 10 expert panel student evaluators.

^aGame selected by student board.

Tools and Budget

After the computer program on STIs and HIV was selected, it was placed on one computer tablet in the waiting area. A Likert-scale questionnaire, developed by this researcher, was designed for study participants to fill out anonymously after they viewed the program. This questionnaire consisted of seven questions (see Appendix D). These questions inquired whether they found the program easy to use, informative, and enjoyable. These questions also asked the participants if they felt they learned more from the computerized format than pamphlets. This study's researcher, faculty chairperson, and committee member reviewed the questions for format, breadth of content, and

relevance. Initially, additional questions were included that related to intention regarding prevention or testing for STIs. However, the university's Institutional Review Board (IRB) felt these questions were too personal and presented the risk of causing distress amongst the study's adolescent population. Therefore, these questions were dropped from the questionnaire. After modifying the questionnaire, the clinic's IRB, the university's IRB, and the Medical Director of the Los Angeles Unified School District approved the study. There were no identifying data other than gender and age to link the subject with the questionnaire answers. The questionnaire took approximately 2-3 minutes to fill out, which was then placed by the students themselves in a locked box.

The budget for the implementation of this program was the cost of one laptop computer, a metal locked box for the collection of questionnaires, and one video on STIs purchased as one of the programs to be considered for the study. The cost of paper and copying was minimal.

Intervention and Data Collection

In order for any patients to be seen by a provider, they must sign the clinic's consent for care. Once the consent was signed, the front office clerk or medical assistant asked the students if they would like to view the new computer education program. The students were instructed that this was part of a quality improvement project study that would update the patient education programs for this clinic. If they were willing to participate, they were given an informational letter explaining the project (Appendix E). This letter was a letter of introduction, which included an explanation of the study. They were then told that they would watch the program and evaluate it using a simple questionnaire. They were also informed that all their responses would remain

anonymous and that they were in no way obligated to evaluate this program and that they had the right to refuse without any consequence or penalty to them. If they agreed to do the evaluation, they were given the computer tablet that contained the *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire* STI game. This was done while the patient was sitting in an empty exam room while waiting to see the provider. Upon completion of the program, they filled out the questionnaire and place it themselves in a locked box prior to seeing the provider. Only this researcher was allowed to collect all the questionnaires at the end of each week. Data collection for this study began in October 2013 and was completed by December 2013. By the end of this study, 55 students had consented to view the program and fill out the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations

Due to the highly sensitive nature of the topic and the subjects' ages, permission to conduct this scholarly project was evaluated and approved by the Medical Director of the Los Angeles Unified School District, the IRB of the study high school clinic, and California State University's IRB.

Every precaution was taken to protect the privacy of the patients and their responses. The questionnaires collected for this study were placed in a locked box that was only opened and analyzed solely by this researcher. No identifying student names, medical record numbers, addresses, or phone numbers were on the questionnaire. This researcher will keep all data for 3 years after the study completion.

This researcher requested, and was granted by the university's IRB, a waiver of documentation of informed consent since this was a quality improvement educational project that would be evaluated by the clinic's expert panel prior to implementation.

There were none to minimal patient physical or psychological risks associated with participating in this study. In order to participate in the study, each student had to have been a registered patient at the high school health center. Due to AB 499, the Minor's Medical Care Consent Law, these students were able to consent to services that allow the providers to provide STI testing, treatment, and patient education without parental or guardian approval. The students were reminded verbally as well as through an informational letter (Appendix E) that they had the right to refuse to participate in the study. Also, the informational letter contained the name and address of the university's IRB should they have any questions or concerns about the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Descriptive statistical analyses were used to determine the results of the questions each of the patients answered after viewing the interactive computerized educational program on STIs and HIV. Statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, Version 20). The purpose of the data analyses was to evaluate the computerized educational program as well as the participants' feelings regarding its usability, enjoyment, prior access to similar types of programs, and reports of improved knowledge from this type of program. The data were examined for differences between gender and adolescent age groups' responses to the same questions. Purposive sampling was done, as each patient was recruited only if he or she signed in to see the provider at the high school health center. A 5-point Likert-type scale, where 1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *neutral*, 4 = *agree*, and 5 = *strongly agree*, seven-question survey was filled out after viewing the program (Appendix D). If the patient was a return visitor and had filled out the survey previously, he or she was allowed to play with the program if he or she wished, but was not allowed to fill out a survey again.

A total of 55 patients, 16 (29%) male and 39 (71%) female, completed the surveys after viewing the program. The students ranged from 14 to 19 years of age. The average mean scores and standard deviations of the entire sample, both genders and all ages, were calculated for each question as seen in Figure 1. The lowest mean score seen was for the question that asked patients if they had accessed similar types of programs ($M = 2.3$, $SD = 1.1$). The second lowest score was for the question that asked if the patients learned more from a computer program than from a printed brochure ($M = 3.5$, $SD = 1.3$). All other mean averages were between 4.5 and 3.9, which showed that this

Figure 1. Mean scores and SD for all patient responses to questionnaire (1 = *strongly disagree* and 5 = *strongly agree*; $N = 55$).

sample population felt that they agreed the program was easy to use, understandable, educational, and enjoyable. The study participants would also like to see more programs like this one made available in the clinic.

Gender Differences

A two-tailed independent samples t test was run to see if there were any significant differences between the male ($n = 16$) and female ($n = 39$) responses to the questions as shown in Table 2. As part of the SPSS program, a comparison of means was done with t testing. A Levene's test for equality of variances was also done for each question to see if equal variances were assumed or not assumed. Significance was set at 0.05. There were no significant differences between male and female responses on all the questions, $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, which was that there were no differences between male and female patients in regard to their responses.

Table 2

Summary of Independent Samples t Tests: Comparisons of Males and Females

Questions	Mean (<i>SD</i>)		<i>t</i> statistic	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> value
	Male	Female			
I found the program easy to use.	4.6 (0.81)	4.5 (0.80)	.318	53	.752
I found the program easy to understand.	4.4 (0.88)	4.5 (0.75)	-.693	53	.491
I would like to see more of these types of programs.	4.2 (0.86)	4.1 (1.00)	.425	53	.672
I have tried to access these types of programs on my computer.	2.6 (1.36)	2.1 (0.99)	1.243	53	.219
I feel I am able to learn more from a computer program than from printed brochures.	3.9 (1.34)	3.3 (1.24)	1.531	53	.132
I learned new information about sexually transmitted infections and their prevention.	3.9 (1.06)	3.9 (0.92)	.229	53	.819
I enjoyed the program.	4.3 (0.87)	4.1 (0.81)	.624	53	.538

Note. Male ($n = 16$), female ($n = 39$), $p = 0.05$.

Age Group Comparison

The responses from the study sample were then divided into two groups: 14- to 16-year-olds ($n = 22$) and 17- to 19-year-olds ($n = 33$). Each group was comprised of males and females. A two-tailed independent samples *t* test was run to compare whether there were any significant differences between how the two age groups responded to the same questions. As part of the SPSS program, a Levene's test for equality of variances was also done for each question to see if equal variances were assumed or not assumed. Significance was set at 0.05. The values for Questions 1-6 were not significant, $p > 0.05$;

therefore, we accepted the null hypothesis that there were no significant differences between age groups for these questions. However, for Question 7, the 14- to 16-years-old group ($M = 4.5$, $SD = 0.74$) enjoyed the program significantly more than the 17- to 19-years-old group ($M = 4.0$, $SD = 0.83$), $t(53) = -2.28$, $p = 0.026$, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis (Table 3).

Table 3

Summary of Independent Samples t Tests: Comparisons of Students Aged 14-16 and Students Aged 17-19

Questions	Mean (SD)		t statistic	df	p value
	Aged 14-16	Aged 17-19			
I found the program easy to use.	4.7 (0.57)	4.4 (0.90)	-1.455	53	.152
I found the program easy to understand.	4.6 (0.58)	4.4 (0.89)	-1.214	53	.230
I would like to see more of these types of programs.	4.1 (0.88)	4.2 (1.01)	.171	53	.865
I have tried to access these types of programs on my computer.	2.0 (0.78)	2.4 (1.27)	1.362	53	.179
I feel I am able to learn more from a computer program than from printed brochures.	3.4 (1.22)	3.6 (1.34)	.339	53	.736
I learned new information about sexually transmitted infections and their prevention.	4.1 (0.92)	3.7 (0.97)	-1.274	53	.208
I enjoyed the program.	4.5 (0.74)	4.0 (0.83)	-2.285	53	.026*

Note. Ages 14-16 years ($n = 22$), ages 17-19 years ($n = 33$).

* $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The computerized educational program on STIs and HIV was very well received by the adolescent patients at the high school health center as shown by the mean scores for each of the questions. Their scores in general indicated that the study group would like to see more of these types of programs become available to them in the clinic. The younger aged adolescent group (14- to 16-year-olds) tended to not only have higher ratings on all the questions, but they enjoyed the program significantly more than the older adolescent group (17- to 19-year-olds). It appears that the younger group enjoyed this type of interactive computerized educational style more than the older group. This outcome reflects the data presented by Lenhart et al. (2010) where they reported that teens age 14-17 years enjoyed computer games and owned more gaming consoles. It can also be speculated that the older group may have felt it was too simple for them. If the older group was more sexually active, perhaps they felt they had enough knowledge on the general information of STIs and wanted more advanced information. However, this researcher could not find data in the literature that spoke to the differences between age groups specifically regarding online programs about STIs. The project director was unable to see if the older adolescents had better scores than the younger adolescents while playing the game. The lack of score keeping was done on purpose because the point of the study was to evaluate the program's usefulness and to get a general feeling about whether the patient learned something about STIs. One of the goals of this school-based clinic is to create an environment that is welcoming and supportive. The clinic does not test the patients on their knowledge after they take and read patient education pamphlets or view a video; therefore, the computerized educational program was held to the same

standards. It was always reinforced to the patients and the clinic staff that this was yet another form of education that may stimulate questions and increase STI awareness, testing, and prevention.

There were fewer boys than girls who visited the clinic at the time of the study. This is a common finding in school-based clinics across the country (Santelli et al., 2003). Even with the small population of boys available for this study ($n = 16$), there was no significant difference in responses between males and females, with both genders rating the program with fairly high scores. This finding reflects the data in that teen boys and girls access social media fairly equally (Lenhart et al., 2010). However, the males who participated in the study found the information on STIs important and applicable, whereas data show that females (23%) more than males (11%) search online for sensitive health information (Lenhart et al., 2010). This project finding regarding the male population's interest in this type of program may be reflective of a growing trend that will discover that more males do want information on STIs. This data should encourage the clinic to find ways to get more males to come to the clinic.

The question that received the lowest scores for both males and females and across age groups was the one that asked whether they had accessed similar types of programs on their own computers. This study's findings seem to be contrary to what some of the other studies are proclaiming regarding teens and their frequent utilization of the Internet to gather information on sexually transmitted diseases (17%). This may be due to the small number of study participants. A larger study may show that more teens access social media for sensitive information. Other considerations for this low score may be that the study participants may have misinterpreted the question, may have no

regular access to computers due to their lower socioeconomic status, or may have found the program and the survey difficult to understand since over 70% of the clinic's clientele are Hispanic and English may not be their primary language. The literature does support the fact that adolescent self-reporting can sometimes be unreliable, especially if they misinterpret the information they are given (L'Engle & Jackson, 2008). This makes having these types of computerized educational programs on STIs, especially if they can be provided in different languages, even more important as educational adjuncts to the patient-provider visit.

Since the computerized educational game on STIs was downloaded onto the laptop computer, there was no risk of patients altering the game. There was also no Internet service for the laptop, so there was also no risk of patients accessing social media and personal email which would have distracted them from playing the game.

Project Limitations

The sample gender distribution was actually a small but accurate representation (71% female) of what is seen in many high school clinics across the country. The overwhelming majority of patients seen in this school-based clinic are female. However, this study only collected data from 55 patients. With a larger sample, there may have been more significant differences between age groups and male and female responses, so the study findings may not be applicable to a larger, ethnically diverse, and more gender balanced group.

Another limitation of this program was that it was only available in English. Over 70% of this clinic's clientele are Hispanic females. While the high school classes are taught in English, it may still not be the adolescents' primary language and therefore the

program may have been difficult to understand for some patients. This may be why the second lowest score was regarding whether the patients felt they learned more from a computer than a pamphlet. In this high school health center, educational pamphlets on STIs and HIV are usually both in English and Spanish. In the future, more computerized health educational programs should be available in both English and Spanish.

Some technical issues did arise during the study. It was found that if the student got a wrong answer, the game ended and did not automatically reset itself. This could not be corrected in the program, so in order to continue playing the game, the patient needed to reset it himself or herself or have someone help him or her reset it. This sometimes presented a problem since it took more time for those students who had to wait for assistance to help them reset it. Also, not all of the students were computer savvy and needed more assistance in playing the game than others. Both these issues presented a problem with time management. Since these are high school students, it was not in the clinic's best interest to keep them for longer periods of time that would cause them to miss their classes. The computer program was limited to 15 questions but not all students were able to finish the whole game before filling out the survey. Only one male student declined to participate in the study, stating that he was in a hurry and did not have time to view the program.

Many of the adolescents who visit this high school health center have a friendly rapport with the staff and providers. Some students come during their break time to just sit and chat with the clinic staff and eat their lunch or snacks in the clinic waiting room. Even though there were no identifiers on the questionnaires and the students themselves placed their responses in a locked box, there is still a possibility that some of the students

rated the computerized educational program much higher than they normally would because they enjoy the clinic and want to please the staff.

Implications for Nursing

Nurses are usually the primary patient advocate and educator in a school-based clinic. Many of these clinics employ nurse practitioners as providers (Keeton et al., 2012). With the increased incidence of sexually transmitted diseases in the adolescent population, nurse practitioners must lead the forefront to improve patient education and encourage STI and HIV awareness, testing, and prevention. Utilization of an interactive computerized patient education program on STIs while the patient is waiting to see the provider could serve as an important adjunct to the face-to-face education the patient receives during the appointment. The nurse practitioner should become involved in creating more of these programs as well as conducting more empirical research in this area since there are very few studies available to validate the usefulness of this type of computer assisted education in school-based clinics. While a few health clinics mentioned in the studies reviewed for this project have used computer assisted learning, there were no data found that specifically reviewed which school-based clinics used this type of patient education. Those few clinics that did use computer assisted learning found that the providers sometimes referenced the computerized program during visits to see if the patients might have specific questions about the information they received. These programs also made the patients more comfortable about asking questions about their sexual health.

Implications for Future Research

Interactive education has been proven to be useful for many types of teaching-learning scenarios in the schools. Many schools will soon be requiring that every student have a computer to use in the classroom. This study's findings show that there may be use for the computer in adolescent patient education. However, there is still such a lack of interactive computerized educational programs in clinics that could serve as adjuncts to the patient-provider visit. These programs should provide medical and psychosocial information for adolescent patients. Future research should be done on a much larger scale to see if this trend of interactive computerized learning could not also work for other school-based clinics. Experimental research and longitudinal studies should be conducted to see if the computerized educational program does indeed enhance knowledge and improve testing and prevention of STIs from all different school-based clinic setting and patient populations.

SBHCs across the country should continue to do research on the utilization of computerized educational programs that would not only be available in the clinic, but also be accessible to the patients via their own computers, iPads, or iPhones. There needs to be more empirical research involving knowledge retention, reduction of high-risk sexual behaviors, increased testing and prevention of STIs, and decreased incidence of STIs related to the use of computerized educational programs.

This project's findings indicated that there were no significant differences between the responses of male and female participants even though the males were the smaller sample size. This data should encourage school-based clinics to provide more outreach to attract male students to their clinics.

Research also needs to occur regarding whether the use of other computerized programs on family planning, pregnancy, diet, exercise, smoking, alcohol abuse, and psychosocial issues might also work in the school-based clinic setting. These programs must be not only accurate, but they must also be enjoyable, stimulate critical thinking, and be culturally sensitive. Perhaps the development of beginning, intermediate, and advanced level programs would better fit the need of these adolescent patients who, as they get older, may want the challenge of being exposed to more complex information. If these types of computerized educational programs can increase adolescents' awareness about the benefits of living a healthier lifestyle, then maybe it would motivate them to change their high-risk and unhealthy behaviors with the support of the staff and their peers.

Conclusion

The implementation of an interactive computerized program on STIs was quite successful. Aside from some of the computer glitches, the adolescent patients enjoyed it and wanted to see more programs of this type in the clinic. School-based clinics can serve as a wonderful and supportive learning environment for their patients. The students, who are also their patients, are used to being in an educational setting and therefore would not find it unusual or out of place to get important health information from clinics. More and more adolescents are using technology and computers to do research and access social media sites. Even though there is not much research on utilizing similar programs for school-based clinics, hospitals, and medical clinics, providers are starting to see the advantages of utilizing computers for patient education. The SBHC should also provide such up-to-date educational formats like an interactive

computerized program to meet adolescent patients' learning needs. Even if most adolescents live with the idea that they are *invincible*, it is still important to constantly reinforce their information on STIs as well as other medical and psychosocial problems common to this population. It is in doing so that adolescents have the opportunity to make informed decisions about their health and reduce their high-risk sexual behaviors.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Acculturation of Hispanic Adolescents and High-Risk Sexual Behaviors

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Adams & Williams (2011)	Exploration of what Mexican American and White female and male adolescents wished they had known about sexual and romantic relationships	Romantic relationships in adolescence can influence future partnerships	Purposive sampling, $n = 75$ 41 Mexican American, 43 White males and females average age 16.04 from 25 different high schools	Qualitative study, phenomenology	Data collected from focus groups discussing what they wished they had known about romantic relationships, themes identified and categorized	No mention of reliability or validity	Teens across ethnicity and gender wanted more information from adults pertaining to romantic and sexual relationships and how to effectively deal with them
Champion et al. (2013)	Exploration of STI health literacy among ethnic minority adolescent women	The Aids Risk Reduction Model (Catania et al., 1990) was used for this study as an explanatory model to assess the association between knowledge of STIs/HIV and sexual risk	Purposive sampling, $N = 559$, 94 African American, 465 Mexican American women 14-18 years of age	Quantitative, descriptive	Questionnaire regarding demographics, psychosocial, situational factors influencing sexual behaviors were given to each subject	Study procedures and researcher training provided inter-rater reliability. Cronbach's alpha (.73) was conducted and validity was suggested since the findings were consistent with	Analyses included contingency tables, t tests and chi-square tests were $p < 0.05$ suggests that Mexican American women are at a higher risk of STIs, pregnancy substance use

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
		behavior in minorities				previous findings regarding minorities and STI/HIV knowledge	and lower level of knowledge about STIs and HIV, lower HIV testing
Kapadia et al. (2012)	Investigation of the association of perceived peer safer sex norms and sexual risk behaviors in substance using Latino adolescents	Theoretical framework based on theories behind the influences of peer pressure on adolescents	Snowball sampling, $n = 92$ Latino adolescents, male and female average age 17.2 who were sexually active and had used marijuana or alcohol within 3 months prior to the study	Quantitative, descriptive	Questionnaire regarding drug an alcohol use, condom use and peer perceptions given to all subjects	Cronbach's alpha (0.82) established reliability, no mention of how validity was established	t Test and logistic regression analysis found that peer influence had a positive impact on condom use $p = 0.027$ where if an adolescent felt their peers were using condoms, they used condoms
Lee & Hahm (2010)	Examination of the longitudinal association between Latina adolescents and high-risk sexual behaviors	No theoretical framework discussed, looked at CDC rates of early initiation of sex amongst teens and increased rates of STDs in adolescents	Systematic sampling and stratification, $N = 1,073$ Latina women between the ages of 18-27 who were sexually active during their young adulthood	Quantitative, descriptive, Data taken from a longitudinal study from 1995-2001 where 7909 females were questioned regarding their sexual health	Questionnaire on sexual health and high-risk behaviors of Latina participants analyzed, Latina subjects placed in 4 sub-groups from foreign born, no English in the home to American born,	Reliability and validity not discussed, however construction of the questionnaire referred back to original National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health (Harris, 2003)	Multivariate analysis with significance set at 0.05, young Latinas who were U.S. born and spoke English in the home had higher rates of diagnoses of STD, 4 or more lifetime sexual

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
					only English in the home		partners and sex after binge drinking. And only the group of foreign born but spoke English in the home had a lower condom use with sex, $p < 0.05$
Schwartz et al. (2012)	Study of acculturation in Hispanic adolescents and associated family functioning and high-risk behaviors	No specific theoretical framework mention, but study based on acculturation theories	Purposive sampling of 266 Hispanic adolescents, $M = 13.4$ yrs, $SD = .68$, and their parents	Randomized clinical trial	Adolescents answered a survey using a computer and language assistance headphones but parents interviewed by Hispanic interviewers	Cronbach's alpha was conducted for surveys and were .91	Chi-square and confidence interval testing showed adolescents who perceived positive family functioning, appeared to be at risk for increased sexual activity and unprotected sex $p < 0.05$
Unger & Molina (2000)	Exploration of the association between acculturation and contraceptive use in Hispanic women	Acculturation among Hispanic women is associated with high-risk sexual behaviors	Purposive sampling, $n = 291$ Hispanic women between the ages of 15-50, who are not currently pregnant	Quantitative, descriptive	Questionnaire regarding demographics, contraceptive use, social support for contraceptive use, cultural	Cronbach's alpha used for all scales, validity not discussed	t Tests conducted to compare means, moderately acculturated women perceived less support for

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Villarruel et al. (2007)	Explore factors predicting Latino condom use	Ajzen (1985) Theory of Planned Behavior	Purposive sampling, $n = 233$ Male and female Latino/Hispanic Avg. age 15.4 years who were recruited from North Philadelphia schools and community centers with large Hispanic/Latino populations	Quantitative, descriptive, randomized control trial	5-point Likert-scale questionnaire given to all subjects in the study	Cronbach's alpha established reliability and validity established because responses mimic results from other similar studies	contraceptive use ($p < 0.05$) Power analysis established n , Pearson product moment correlation utilized with significance set at 0.05, Hedonistic beliefs, condom use self-efficiency, impulse control, partner negotiation, partner and parent approval predicts condom use ($p < 0.05$)

APPENDIX B

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Adolescents and High-Risk Sexual Behaviors

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Gray et al. (2005)	Explore the perceptions of adolescents from the United Kingdom and United States regarding online health information and their experiences with its using this medium	No mention of model or theoretical framework, but discussed how the Internet is used most frequently by adolescents as seen through previous studies	Purposive sampling from secondary schools in US and UK <i>n</i> = 157 male and female students, average between the ages of 11-19, from the UK and US	Qualitative, interview	26 single-gender groups were convened and asked about Internet use for health issues and responses were recorded and coded for themes	No mention of reliability or validity in this study	Strong over-arching themes across both countries due to online access to the same types of programs with increasing practice of these adolescents using the Internet to seek health information
L'Engle & Jackson (2008)	Investigation of sexual risk before the adolescent initiates sexual intercourse thereby enabling the provider to guide the adolescent from high risk sexual behaviors	Cognitive susceptibility of adolescents regarding the initiation of high risk behaviors has long been studied in psychology	Purposive sampling, <i>n</i> = 854 7 th and 8 th graders, males and females, multi-ethnic who had not had sexual intercourse	Quantitative, longitudinal	Likert-scale survey given to each adolescent at baseline in 2002 and follow-up 2004 on topics that could predict likelihood to initiating sex	Cronbach's alpha was used for reliability (0.77) and construct validity established in this study through a variety of tests	Logistic regression analysis found that 38% nonsusceptible, 34% low susceptibility, 28% high susceptibility to initiating sex after 2 years, also those

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Secor-Turner et al. (2013)	Explore whether an adolescent's familial and social environment can predict high-risk sexual behaviors	Social Ecological Model used to examine interplay between environment and behaviors	Data collected from a cohort of adolescents who were in a previous randomized trial called Primetime. <i>n</i> = 241 Sexually active females between the ages of 13-17, recruited from two school-based clinics and two community clinics in Minneapolis and St. Paul	Quantitative, longitudinal	Questionnaire applied at baseline and at 6 month follow-up that measured the relationship between the adolescent's family dysfunction and individual risk factors and condom use and number of male sex partners at baseline and at 6 months	Cronbach's alpha established reliability (0.71, 0.83, 0.91) for various sections of the questionnaire, validity not discussed	highly susceptible had poor relationships with parents, more physically mature, peers sexually active and had greater sexual feelings Structured equation modeling and factor analyses applied, baseline level of individual risk was positively associated with number of sex partners, but not condom use 6 months later (path coefficient 0.2), level of family dysfunction was negatively associated with condom use but not the number of sex partners at 6-month

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results point (-0.3)
Wickman et al. (2008)	Explore phenomenon of invincibility in adolescents	Elkind (1970) Social and cognitive development of adolescents	Stratified sampling, <i>n</i> = 10, Male/female Multiethnic adolescents selected based on age, gender and ethnicity	Qualitative, phenomenology	Semi-structured interviews with questions developed from literature review regarding invincibility in teens	Reliability not mentioned, however study finding validated since it is similar to findings from previous studies	Themes emerged called adolescence a time of transition, invincibility, balancing and risk taking

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Computers and Health Information Seeking by Adolescents

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Bull et al. (2012)	To determine whether messages on STD prevention via digital media are effective in reducing high risk sexual behavior	No theoretical framework or model discussed, however study was based on data showing increased STDs and lack of prevention in adolescents	Respondent driven sampling, $n = 1,578$, male and female, ages 16-25, multi-ethnic, U.S. citizens and owners of a Facebook page were recruited from multiple settings	Quantitative, clustered randomized controlled trial	Treatment group exposed to online media, via Facebook, on STIs and prevention. Both groups tested at 2 months and 6 months via questionnaire regarding condom use	No discussion of reliability or validity in the study	t Tests and chi-square tests done and at 2 months the treatment group had higher condom use ($p = 0.04$). However, at 6 months no significant differences between both groups on condom use
Howard et al. (2011)	An exploratory study to see whether low income minority teens can benefit from an Internet computer educational program to decrease high risk sexual	No mention of model or conceptual framework, however discussion about rising STDs in minority adolescents and lack of online resources is what	Convenience sampling, $n = 109$, male and female adolescents who attend a family planning clinic in a large public hospital	Quantitative, exploratory	Random selection of two groups, both groups filled out a pre and postquestionnaire. The treatment group received a computerized PowerPoint lesson and website	No mention of reliability or validity in this study	Chi-square analysis showed the treatment group had an increase in condom use and knowledge of high-risk behaviors ($p < 0.05$) at the 3 and 6 month

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
	behaviors	drove this study			information regarding high-risk sexual behaviors, the control group was only asked to fill out the questionnaire		marks
Jones & Biddlecom (2011)	Exploratory study to assess how adolescents use the Internet for sexual health information	No model discussed, study based on knowledge that more adolescents and educational systems are using computers and relying on digital education	Respondent driven sampling, <i>n</i> = 58 Male/female junior and senior multi-ethnic high school students in New York and Indiana	Qualitative Exploratory	Each teen interviewed utilizing a set of questions aimed at gathering information on their Internet use for researching sexual health issues	No mention of reliability or validity in the article	Many of these teens knew sites on sexual health existed but the majority of them did not access the Internet for contraception and abstinence, because the researchers had to obtain informed parental consent for the study, it was speculated that these teens may have been worried about revealing that they are actively looking for information on sexual health

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
Kiene & Barta (2006)	To find alternate and innovative ways to deliver HIV/AIDS risk-reduction intervention and education	Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model provides the conceptual basis for this study	Purposive sampling from the university's psychology dept. $n = 157$, male and female, average age 18.86, multi-ethnic, unmarried	Quantitative, experimental	Treatment group were exposed to computerized education on HIV/AIDs and prevention. Analysis via questionnaire on condom use between the two groups was done at the 4 week mark	No mention of reliability, however the researchers assumed validity since the findings were comparable to similar studies	ANCOVA analysis at 4 weeks, there was improved condom use by the treatment group ($p < 0.05$)
Noar et al. (2006)	Review of 21 on Interactive Safer Sex websites	No theoretical framework discussed	Search of websites between 9/10-10/24/04 using various search engines found hundreds of potential sites	Literature/ Website Review	Each site had to meet the following: English language, focused on safe sex, had to contain at least 2 interactive features. 21 sites were found	Two different coders coded each website and when both reports merged agreed on these 21 websites indicating good inter-coder agreement	The Internet has the ability to change high-risk sexual behaviors by providing interactive computerized health education
Roberto et al. (2007)	Assessment of a computer-based education program on STD and HIV prevention in rural adolescents	Extended Parallel Process Model (EPPM) (Witte, 1992) used to inform the development of an intervention and identify outcomes that	Purposive sampling, Control group, $n = 337$, Male/female average age 14.37 years, Treatment group $N = 550$, Male/female and	Quantitative, quasi-experimental	Pre and posttests were done on both groups after 3 months. The treatment group received six computer-based activities	The study used well established instruments in the pre and posttests proving reliability and validity as results were very similar to previous results	ANOVA testing with significance set at 0.05, treatment group improved knowledge, use of condoms, perceived greater

Author/Year	Purpose	Theoretical Framework	Participants	Design	Intervention	Reliability/ Validity	Measurements/ Results
		will assist when looking to change high risk behaviors	average age 14.49. Majority of both groups were European American, all from 9 rural high schools			from use of these tools	susceptibility to HIV and favorable attitudes toward waiting for initiation of sex, $p < 0.05$

APPENDIX D

EVALUATION OF COMPUTER LEARNING PROGRAM FOR SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED INFECTIONS

AGE _____ Gender: M F

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. I found the program easy to use.	5	4	3	2	1
2. I found the program easy to understand.	5	4	3	2	1
3. I would like to see more of these types of programs.	5	4	3	2	1
4. I have tried to access these types of programs on my computer.	5	4	3	2	1
5. I feel I am able to learn more from a computer program than from printed brochures.	5	4	3	2	1
6. I learned new information about sexually transmitted infections and their prevention.	5	4	3	2	1
7. I enjoyed this program.	5	4	3	2	1

APPENDIX E

INFORMATION LETTER

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, Los Angeles

Innovative Computerized Patient Education Program on Sexually Transmitted Infections

INFORMATION FORM

This computerized patient education program, conducted by Jean O'Neil, as part of the requirements for the DNP degree in Nursing, is a project where we are evaluating whether you feel this type of program is useful and informative about sexually transmitted infections.

Each participant will be asked by the front office clerk whether they would like to view and evaluate the program as they sign in as a patient here at **the High School Health Clinic**. (Took out the name of the clinic for this paper to protect the minors)

With regard to risks in participation with this project, there are minimal physical or psychological risks in participating in this project.

After viewing the patient education program, you will answer a short questionnaire evaluating the program. Your answers will remain anonymous and will be placed, by you, in a locked box. The researcher will not record any identifiable information about the subject. The cumulative results of this study may be published, but the names or identity of subjects will not be made known. All data/documentation collected as part of this project will be destroyed by the researcher at the conclusion of the study.

The participants will not receive monetary compensation for participation in this study.

You should understand that approval for you to participate in this study is completely voluntary, and you may decline to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without jeopardy.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE DEAN OF GRADUATE STUDIES AND RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-3798).